

EFFECT OF PROCESSING VARIABLES ON THE PULTRUSION PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

A numerical model of pultrusion process has been developed to predict the effect of processing variables such as die wall temperature, pulling speed and fiber contents. This model was based on the concept of shrinkage phenomenon due to resin cure. Pressure and center line temperature distributions were measured on the proto-type pultruder and compared with the numerical results. It was found that the predicted values were in good agreement with those of the experiments. The properties of composite profile by pultrusion were obtained by DMA experiment. The property change of composite material due to processing variables could be successfully illustrated through the internal behavior (such as thermal history) and the external behavior (such as pulling speed) imposed.

KEYWORDS; Pultrusion; Thermosetting; Processing; Property; Interphase

1. INTRODUCTION

Pultrusion process is recently used to fabricate high performance composite materials by impregnating resin in the continuous reinforcements. Especially, the pultrusion process can produce almost unlimited length, more flexible and higher tensile strength of the reinforced composite than any other reactive polymer processes[1-4]. In spite of its commercial viabilities and potential, relatively little work[5-12] has been done, because the process is difficult to control unless one knows how to effectively impregnate the reinforcement with thermosetting material in the resin bath and how to handle the exothermic chemical reactions and flow phenomena taking place in the pultrusion die.

The purpose of this study is concerned with developing a numerical model to accurately predict the behaviors in the heated die, by introducing the appropriate reaction kinetics, chemorheology, heat transfer, fluid mechanics which are relevant for the pultrusion of reactive resin. Also in order to discover the effect of processing variables on the property of pultruded composite material, the glass transition temperature and creep behavior were examined.

2. THEORETICAL

2.1 Heat Transfer Model We make the following assumptions for predicting the temperature and conversion profile inside the heated die.

- 1) Bulk heat transfer by back flow is negligible, hence the heat transfer model is uncoupled with the pressure model.
- 2) Axial heat conduction is negligible
- 3) The resin and fiber have the same temperature at any point in the die.
- 4) Reaction rate is unaffected by the fiber and pressure.

In the rectangular coordinate, the heat transfer and cure kinetic equations[13] can be simplified by

$$u_z \rho c_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} = k \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \right) + H_u \frac{d\alpha}{dt} (1 - u_f) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k \frac{1}{\alpha_{max}} \alpha^m (\alpha_{max} - \alpha)^n, \quad m + n = 2 \quad (2)$$

where u_z is a pulling speed, ρ density, c_p the heat capacity, k thermal conductivity of the composite system, α is the extent of cure reaction, H_u is ultimate heat of reaction, and u_f is a weight fraction of the glass fiber. Kinetic parameters are determined by DSC experiments.

The thermophysical properties of the composite system are calculated as follows[14]:

$$\rho = \phi_r \rho_r + \phi_f \rho_f \quad (3)$$

$$\rho_r = \rho_o / [1 + 3 \mathcal{E}_v (T - T_o) - \gamma \alpha] \quad (4)$$

$$c_p = u_r c_{pr} + u_f c_{pf} \quad (5)$$

$$k = (1 - \sqrt{\phi_f}) k_r + k_m \sqrt{\phi_f} / [1 - \sqrt{\phi_f} (1 - k_r / k_f)] \quad (6)$$

where ϕ is volume fraction and u is weight fraction and subscripts r and f refer to resin and fiber, respectively, \mathcal{E}_v is thermal expansion coefficient and γ is the shrinkage fraction of the resin.

The initial conditions are given by

$$T(x, y, 0) = T_o \quad (7)$$

$$\alpha(x, y, 0) = 0 \quad (8)$$

Symmetric boundary conditions are applied at the center plane of the composite profile. Initially, the resin is in good thermal contact with the heated die, so the isothermal wall boundary conditions are used.

$$T(x,H,t)=T_{\text{wall}}, \quad T(L,y,t)=T_{\text{wall}} \quad (9)$$

But as the composite profile shrinks away from the die due to resin cure, equation (9) is no longer applicable. So convective boundary conditions may be used.

$$\partial T(L,y,t)/\partial x = - (h_{\text{air}} / k) [T(L,y,t) - T_{\text{wall}}] \quad (10)$$

$$\partial T(x,H,t)/\partial y = - (h_{\text{air}} / k) [T(x,H,t) - T_{\text{wall}}] \quad (11)$$

where h_{air} is heat transfer coefficient of air. The point of separation is determined when the thermal expansion of resin is less than the shrinkage during cure, i.e.

$$\epsilon_v (\bar{T} - T_{\text{amb}}) - \gamma \bar{\alpha} < 0 \quad (12)$$

where \bar{T} and $\bar{\alpha}$ are average temperature and conversion across the composite profile.

2.2 Pressure Model The model is based on the assumptions that the fibers act like an anisotropic porous media, and any hydrodynamic fluid motion around individual fiber will be ignored. Glass fiber is uniformly distributed in the resin system and resin flow is at steady state. Permeant surface tension of the resin is similar to silicone oil.

The relative resin velocity through porous media is directly proportional to the pressure gradient, so Darcy's law[15] is modified for pultrusion process as follows:

$$u_r = \frac{\psi}{\eta} \nabla p \quad (13)$$

where η is the resin viscosity, and ψ is the permeability tensor which is a function of fiber radius r_f , fiber volume fraction ϕ_f , and Kozeny constant K'_c .

$$\psi = \frac{(r_f)^2 (1 - \phi_f)^3}{4K'_c \phi_f^2} \quad (14)$$

Lam and Kardos[16] and Gutowski[17] had experimented the permeability for a concentrated fiber bed and verified similar results. In this study, the transverse Kozeny constant is 11 and the axial Kozeny constant is 0.35, respectively.

Equation(13) is inserted into the fluid continuity equation to express the dependence of fluid viscosity, and codeformational coordinate was used because volume fraction does change in the axial direction due to the entrance taper of the die. The codeformational coordinate $a(y)$ expresses location in terms of the constant volume of fiber enclosed in a rectangular of thickness y .

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial a} \left(\frac{\psi_y}{\eta} \rho_r \phi_f \frac{\partial p}{\partial a} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{\psi_z}{\eta \phi_f} \rho_r \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} \right) = v_z \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left\{ \frac{(1-\phi_f)}{\phi_f} \rho_r \right\} \quad (15)$$

where $a = \phi_f y$.

The initial and boundary conditions of the pressure model are as follows:

$$p(a, 0) = 0 \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial a}(\phi_f H, z) = 0 \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial a}(0, z) = 0 \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial z}(a, z_{ge1}) = 0 \quad (19)$$

Viscosity changes of a commercial vinyl ester resin system had been characterized by Lee[13] to be following form

$$\eta = \eta_\infty \exp(E_\eta / RT) f(\alpha) \quad (20)$$

$$f(\alpha) = (1+\alpha)/(1-\alpha/\alpha_{ge1}), \alpha < \alpha_{ge1} \quad (21)$$

$$\eta = \infty, \alpha \geq \alpha_{ge1} \quad (22)$$

After the resin gelled, it can not flow and hence Darcy's law is not valid. Therefore, the resin continuity equation is useful in the region before gel line of the composite profile. The heat transfer and pressure model equations were solved by finite difference method.

3. Experimental

3.1 Materials and Equipment A commercial vinyl ester resin (DERAKANE 411-45, Dow Chemical) and Benzoyl Peroxide (FLUKA CHEMIE AG) as an initiator were used in this study. The resin mixture was contained 1 phr BPO in vinyl ester resin. The composite profiles involved 76, 79.3, and 82 wt% of glass fiber.

To perform the pultrusion experiment, we used the proto-type pultruder. The dimension of heated die was 15 x 3.3 x 1100 mm and entrance zone was opened up to 100mm which included taper zone. The detailed procedures are well described in reference[13,18].

3.2 Methods of Property Analysis Dynamic mechanical properties of pultruded composite were obtained by fixed frequency method using a Du Pont 983 dynamic mechanical analyzer operated by a 9900 data acquisition system. For measuring the storage and loss moduli and the damping factor of samples, temperature range was used from 30°C to 300°C at heating rate 2°C/min. The used frequency was 1 Hz.

To measure the creep compliance of the composite samples, experimental temperature range was used from 30°C to 150°C including the stepwise increment of 10°C. The constant external force, which was approximately 56 kPa, was maintained for 10 min for the measurement of creep compliance at a given temperature, and thereafter relaxed for 20 min at each step temperature. This procedure continued up to 150°C.

4. Results and Discussion

We could evaluate parameters of cure kinetics and chemorheological behavior through the comparison with theory and experiments[13], as follows:

$$E_k = 79967 \quad [\text{J/mol}]$$

$$\text{at } \alpha < 0.15 \quad k_o = 7.597 \text{ E8 } [1/\text{sec}], \quad m = 0.654$$

$$\text{at } \alpha \geq 0.15 \quad k_o = 1.616 \text{ E8 } [1/\text{sec}], \quad m = 0.806$$

and

$$A = 1.488 \text{ E-9} \quad [\text{Pa. sec}]$$

$$E_\eta = 52310 \quad [\text{J/mol}]$$

4.1 Analysis of Pultrusion Process Numerical simulations, introducing above parameters, and experiments were carried out at various operating conditions such as pulling speeds and die wall temperature distributions. Especially, center line temperature distribution of the composite profile and pressure distribution along the die wall were measured experimentally, and compared with predicted results. And the detailed die wall temperature conditions are presented in Table 1.

According to experiments, a perfectly contacted condition between composite profile and the heated die is not maintained due to shrinkage of thermosetting resin by curing, so it is necessary to modify the surface temperature of the composite profile by introducing the weighting factor, ϑ .

$$T(x,H,t) = T_{\text{wall}} (1 - \vartheta) + T_{\text{wn}} \vartheta \quad (23)$$

where T_{wn} is calculated from equations (10), (11), and (12). Thus one could consider two cases: a) composite profile perfectly contacts with die wall, and b) composite profile perfectly separates from die wall in pultrusion die. We found that the real separating condition was in between the two cases. In this study, the value of weighting factor, ϑ , was approximately 0.75 up to pulling speed of 60 cm/min.

Figure 1 shows centerline and surface temperature distributions of composite profile, viscosity change of thermosetting resin, and pressure distribution along the die length at a typical processing condition. This figure indicates all phenomenological behaviors which occur in the heated die during the processing. According to the numerical simulation results, especially, the position of separating point of composite profile occurs incipient gel point, and the surface temperature of composite near the separating point is slightly lower than the die wall temperature because the convective heat transfer occurs in the air gap between the die wall and the surface of composite profile. And also, conversion at the surface of composite profile approaches to completely cured state earlier than that at center of composite. In addition, we were able to discover that the

pressure is mainly built up in the tapered zone, because the excess resin is squeezed out from the resin-impregnated reinforcement in this zone. After leaving the tapered zone, however, the pressure decreases along the die length owing to a decrease of the resin viscosity up to a certain position near the gel point. Finally, at the gel point, it is difficult for the resin to flow in the fiber bed because of the rapid increase of resin viscosity, so the constant value of pressure is maintained in this region as a final pressure.

Figure 2 shows the centerline temperature distribution of composite profile along the die length at various processing conditions presented in Table 1. This figure exhibits that the position of maximum peak temperature is highly dependent upon the die wall temperature conditions due to the curing behavior of reactive resin.

4.2 Glass Transition Temperature by Effect of Interphase Figure 3 shows a typical result from DMA measurement on a sample of composite profile by pultrusion. There are two peaks in $\tan \delta$ curve, the peak 1 is believed the glass transition temperature of matrix in composite material, because the flexural storage modulus against temperature is strongly dependent upon the peak 1[19,20].

In order to identify the behavior of another peak at even higher temperature, peak 2, more clearly, we measured the $\tan \delta$ behavior of composite sample with respect to fiber content and orientation effects by DMA experiment, as shown in Figures 4 and 5. The $\tan \delta$ value of peak 1 decreases with increase of fiber contents, but that of peak 2 increases with fiber contents. And also the peak 2 disappears as the angle of fiber orientation with respect to the clamping direction is changed from 0 to 90 degrees. This is in good agreement with the results of Reed[21] that is related to an interphase. It is considered that the peak 2 in the $\tan \delta$ curve occurs due to the interphase boundary between fiber surface and resin matrix.

4.3 Glass Transition Temperature by Processing condition Figure 6 shows temperatures of peak 1 and 2 of composite profiles as a function of pulling speed with respect to various die wall temperature conditions. For peak 2, the temperature gradually decreases with increasing the pulling speed and with decreasing the maximum temperature of heated die wall at a given pulling speed.

On the other hand, temperature of peak 1 against the pulling speeds shows similar trends besides case 4. This means that the glass transition temperature of matrix in composite is strongly dependent on the thermal

history, because case 1, 2, and 3 have the similar thermal behavior, as shown in Figure 2. Also, the glass transition temperature of matrix for the case 4 shows higher value than those of other cases for all pulling speeds. This is believed to be caused by relatively long residence time at higher temperature condition comparing with other cases, which may contribute to the resin cure.

4.4 Creep Behavior by Processing Condition The simplest creep experiment involves step loading a fixed stress to a material[19,20], then the strain as a function of time is measured. Figure 7 shows a successful application of Time-Temperature-Superposition to creep compliances of composite materials at various pulling speeds under a given die wall temperatures(case 2). The creep compliance of composite sample increases with the pulling speed up to a certain speed and thereafter exhibits approximately same value regardless of pulling speeds. The changes of creep behavior are well corresponding to the trend of the glass transition temperature of matrix rather than that of interphase, as shown in Figure 6. Consequently, the long term durability of composite material is mainly dependent up on the glass transition temperature of matrix because the properties of matrix may affect on the composite material as a defect.

5. Conclusions

A numerical simulation model based on the concept of shrinkage phenomenon by resin cure was developed for the pultrusion process. It was found that the predicted values of pressure and center line temperature along the die length were in good agreement with those of the experiments. The glass transition temperatures of matrix and interphase boundary in composite material were detected by means of DMA experiment. From the relationship between the results of DMA experiment and processing variables, it was found that the creep compliance mainly depends on the glass transition temperature of matrix in composite profile which is influenced by its thermal history, without regard to that of interphase boundary.

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Table 1. Die wall temperature for pultrusion experiments.

LENGTH(m)	CASES				
	case1	case2	case3	case4	case5
0.000	40 ⁰ C	41 ⁰ C	40 ⁰ C	70 ⁰ C	75 ⁰ C
0.086	47	43	42	94	105
0.395	65	63	63	140	147
0.575	92	105	103	140	147
0.697	121	134	152	140	147
0.817	150	170	190	140	147
0.947	150	170	190	140	147
1.10	150	160	178	140	147

FIGURE 1. A typical diagram of various phenomena in the composite profile for case 1 at pulling speed = 40 cm/min.

FIGURE 2. Distribution of centerline temperature versus die length, resulted from numerical simulation at pulling speed = 20 cm/min for case 1-5.

FIGURE 3. A typical diagram resulted from DMA experiment for composite material. Heating rate = 2°C/min, 1 Hz.

FIGURE 4. A typical diagram resulted from DMA experiment for composite material with respect to fiber orientation angle. Heating rate = 2°C/min at 1Hz.

FIGURE 5. A typical diagram resulted from DMA experiment for composite material with respect to fiber contents. Heating rate = 2°C/min at 1Hz.

FIGURE 6. Temperature of peak 1 and 2 of composite material by DMA versus pulling speed for cases 1, 2, 3, and 4. Heating rate = 2°C/min, 1 Hz.

FIGURE 7. Creep compliance of composite material versus time at various pulling speed for case 2.